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UNDERSTANDING THE ENVIRONMENT TO CONTRIBUTE TO THE CONSERVATION OF THE STINGLESS BEE SPECIES MELIPONA MANDACAIA

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Abstract

The *Melipona mandacaia* is a stingless bee found along the São Francisco River and its tributary streams¹. It is an endemic species from the Caatinga, a unique biome located in the semi-arid region of Northeastern Brazil that experiences critical climatic events, such as recurring droughts, with areas at risk of desertification². The species is also widely used by the local population in meliponiculture, making it economically important for the region as well³. Considering the importance of the habitat for the survival of the *Melipona mandacaia*, a review was conducted, utilizing literature, governmental

websites, official documents, and georeferencing data to better characterize the area. The colonies used as reference points for this study were sampled from multiple locations, including both natural and urban sites, to ensure a comprehensive understanding of their habitat. To achieve this, climatological data, geodiversity, vegetation, solar irradiation, and land use were analyzed. Improper land use was identified in the region, with areas of agriculture and livestock farming. Distinct geodiversity was also identified among some of the sampled areas, which may influence the mineral profile of the honey and the plant species present in those locations. Additionally, the high incidence of solar radiation may affect the bees' flight and foraging, as discussed in previous studies⁴. By highlighting relevant features, this study aims contribute to a better characterization of the habitat of the *Melipona mandacaia*, ensuring the improved preservation of the species and the maintenance of the area where it is found. This information is crucial for developing effective conservation strategies, promoting sustainable land use practices, and raising awareness about the importance of protecting the Caatinga biome. Lastly, further studies must be carried out to identify the relationship of geodiversity in honey profile.

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